

ASSESSING THE INFLUENCE OF FLAX FIBERS HUMIDITY ON PROPERTIES AND MANUFACTURING AT CONTROLLED CAPILLARY NUMBER

Jean-Baptiste Jouenne¹, Antoine Levée² Bernard Miranda Campos³ and Joël Bréard¹

¹ABTE, UR 4651 Université de Caen Normandie,
Bd Maréchal Juin, 14032 Caen, France
Email: jean-baptiste.jouenne@unicaen.fr

²DEPESTELE/Teillage Vandecandelaère, Research & Development, 14540 Bourguébus, France

³Laboratoire CRISMAT, Normandie Université, ENSICAEN, UNICAEN, CNRS,
14050 Caen, France

Keywords: Liquid Composite Molding, Natural Fiber, Moisture Effect , Controlled flow rate

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a new method to perform liquid composite molding with a controlled resin flow rate, enabling the manufacture of plant fiber-reinforced composites with varying water contents. The manufacturing of plant fiber composites is still poorly controlled, as existing techniques are often adapted from synthetic fiber composites, despite the hydrophilic nature of natural fibers making such transpositions problematic. We propose that by monitoring fiber water content, it is possible to master the manufacturing process and optimize the structural integrity of the final part. To achieve this, we developed a novel infusion method that maintains a constant resin flow front velocity and allows processing at a target Capillary number (Ca). Our results show that drying natural fibers is not always necessary for successful infusion. This work demonstrates that composite parts can be manufactured while preserving fiber integrity, reducing energy consumption, and minimizing environmental impact.

1 INTRODUCTION

The manufacturing of plant fiber-reinforced composites has been a challenge since the beginning of the 21st century. It has been established that the plant fibers specificities, all the more so flax fibers, differ from those of synthetic ones. One of the major differences between these two types of materials lies in the hydrophilic nature of plant fibers. Many studies have shown that during the processing of such composites, controlling the amount of water contained by the fibers to improve understanding microstructural material state [1]. Moreover, manufacturing processes used for plant fiber-reinforced composites are mostly carried out through the direct transposition of methods and technologies used for the production of synthetic ones. This approach does not ensure preservation of the structural integrity of the flax fibers, nor does it optimize the properties of the composite material produced. Liquid composite molding processes (LCM) such as resin infusion are commonly used in many industrial fields to fabricate composites [2]. In liquid resin infusion, the pressure difference between the polymer bucket and the mold outlet drives the polymer flow [3]. As the polymer flow front progresses into the fibrous preform, the pressure gradient decreases. Consequently, the velocity v of the polymer flow front also decreases with time. Using the capillary number (Ca) in injection process, where μ is the liquid viscosity and γ the liquid/gas surface tension, authors [4] have demonstrated the necessity to monitor polymer flow front velocity in order to minimize the void content in the final composite part.

In addition to these physical parameters, the water contained by plant fibers can have a significant impact during processing. Due to the hydrophilic nature of plant fibers, their moisture sorption mechanisms have been widely studied in a wide range of humid environments [5]. Authors have highlighted that “water sorption in fibers and their composites has been found to significantly affect their dimensional and structural properties”. Therefore, when compressing preforms, hygro-thermal

conditions must also be controlled and monitored, in order to take hygro-mechanical specificities of plant fibers into account. Other authors [6], [7] showed that water contained in plant fibers also influences the resin crosslinking.

Recently, a low-tech dedicated setup has been developed in the laboratory allowing to control the flow front velocity v . This study aims to introduce a unique research tool in the field of composite manufacturing by liquid infusion process allowing scientist the study of natural fibers processability at controlled Ca . Using fiber's moisture management, it is first proposed to measure the influence of humidity on properties and manufacturing of natural fiber reinforced composites. A second outlook for this work is to show that our new setup enables the manufacturing of optimized plant fiber-reinforced composite parts by piloting resin flow at the appropriate Ca .

This work is the starting point of a project that aims at bringing new insights on liquid composites manufacturing processes using low environmental impact technologies and to the formation of microstructural defects.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Description of the research tool

The upper mold is a 20 mm thick transparent glass to prevent mold deformation and the lower part of the mold is an aluminum plate of 10 mm thick (figure 1a). Spacers of predefined thickness are placed on the side of mold to obtain final parts of the target thickness. In this study, spacers of 3 mm will be use to reach 30 % volumetric fiber fraction with 4 flax plies. Two grooves are cut in the lower part of the mold and seals are placed in them creating two cavities: the inner cavity in which the preform is placed, and the outer cavity in which a vacuum is done (figure 1b). This vacuum is referred to as *peripheral vacuum* reaches -980 mbar and is the first novelty of this method. Because vacuum is not directly applied on the preform stack as in most of LCM processes, the resin is allowed to freely go through the preform. In addition, the *peripheral vacuum* applies on the preform a constant pressure of around 0.1 MPa which is used for fiber compaction. The second novelty of this method is the use of a peristaltic pump to transfer resin from the reservoir to the preform. A peristaltic pump can transfer fluids without exposing them to contamination for example for sterile or corrosive fluids. It is mainly used for pharmaceutical, medical and agro application. The principle is that a flexible tubing is mounted inside a circular pump housing with rotating rollers. As the rollers turns, the tube is compressed then released continuously causing the fluid to circulate in one direction (figure 1a). With the combination of these two principles, fiber preform can be impregnated at controlled flow rate and constant flow front velocity. The pump is a Masterflex™ L/S™ capable of delivering a constant flow rate from 0.36 to 3400 mL/min, with a reverse flow option that is particularly useful for cleaning the hoses after manufacturing. Hoses are made from silicone with an outer diameter of 7 mm and an inner diameter of 5 mm. Before the preform impregnation, both parts of the mold are waxed and polished with a release agent to facilitate demolding. The preform is then positioned inside the mold, with a gutta seal placed around it to minimize edge effects during the impregnation. Then the peripheral vacuum is applied to compact the preform. After compaction, a 15 minutes relaxation phase is done to reach target thickness before starting impregnation. The resin will first full the space at the inlet of the cavity where there are no fibers (figure 2a). Once this space is full, the resin will go through the preform with a perfect straight line of flow front (figure 2b). Once filled, the resin progresses through the preform with a straight flow front (Figure 2b). When the resin reaches the end of the preform, the pump is stopped and the inlet tube is clamped to prevent leakage. The tube is then cut, and any remaining resin is returned to the reservoir using the pump's reverse function. The tube is cleaned with ethanol followed by water, allowing it to be reused. Demolding is done by releasing the peripheral vacuum. Disposable items include the section of hose embedded in cured resin, the gutta seal, and the resin container.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the *THMClight* experimental setup

The fabrics used are 2 x 2 linen twills with a weight per unit area of 300 g/m² meter supplied by *Depestel (Teillage Vandecandelaere, France)*. The polymer used is an epoxy-amine system consisting of *Greenpoxy SR8100* epoxy precursor and *SD8824* amine hardener, both supplied by *SICOMIN*. The experimental setup was designed to be low-tech, requiring only long-life equipment and very few consumables (hoses, mixing pot, sealant tape).

For conditioning, the linen fabrics were stored in a humidity-controlled enclosure at a constant temperature of 23°C. The storage time for the plies was based on a prior assessment of the time required to reach water saturation. Parameters and resulting water content are described in table 1.

Designation	HR0%	HR50%	HR70%	HR90%
Relative humidity	0	50	70	90
Temperature	103	23	23	23
Conditioning time (h)	24	24	24	24
Water content (wt%)	0 - 2	7,6	9,9	16,7
Density (kg/m ³)	1490	1470	1465	1420

Table 1: Preform conditioning

2.2 Measuring the flow front velocity

Since the main objective of the THMClight is to impregnate fibrous preforms at a controlled flow rate, it is essential to measure the flow front velocity. THMClight is, above all, a research tool designed to help scientists and industrial partners better understand impregnation mechanism. The upper mold is made of glass allowing user to observe the progression of the resin flow front. A camera is installed above the experimental set up to capture the entire impregnation phase (figure 2). After the recording, the flow front velocity of the resin is measured with FIJI (ImageJ). After setting the scale, a straight line was drawn between the edge of the preform at the onset of impregnation and the resin front. A value noted as X_t , corresponding to the position of the resin front over time, was then determined (figure 2).

Figure 2: Resin flow front progression through a dry preform at constant rate

By plotting the graph $X_t = f(t)$, a series of data points was obtained, enabling the characterization of the resin front advancement profile. A linear regression of this dataset (constrained to pass through the origin) is performed to determine the velocity at which the resin front propagates through the preform.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Validation of the tool

The main objective of the *THMClight* was to allow liquid composite manufacturing at constant resin flow front. Validation of the tool was conducted by manufacturing composite plates reinforced with dry flax fibers at a flow rate corresponding to optimal capillary number ($Ca_{opt} \approx 10^{-3}$) as proposed by other researchers [8], [9], [10], [11]. The pump speed was set to 15 rpm (22.5 mL/min) and manufacturing done in triplicate to demonstrate the robustness of the method. The evolution of the resin front position over time for each trial is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Resin flow front position (X_t) over time during manufacturing ($Q = 22,5$ mL/min)

Each point on the graph corresponds to the position of the resin front along the plate over time. A measurement was taken approximately every 2 cm along the plate. During controlled flow impregnation, the resin front formed a straight line with an angular deviation between 0 and 5°. Edge effects that can distort this front were occasionally observed and are attributed to poor distribution of the yarns along the parting line typically due to the absence of a yarn in the X-direction. Owing to the regularity of the resin front, the X_t values could be measured at the center of the plate during impregnation. The resulting plot is a linear function, which confirms that the resin front advances at a constant velocity. The average value of the flow front rate is $1,02 \pm 0,03$ mm/s which is in good agreement with other researchers that succeed to impregnate synthetic fibers at controlled flow rate [8], [11].

3.2 Influence of preform water content

Multiple composite plates were manufactured using different flow rates to target various Ca . Preform with various fiber water contents were also used to assess the influence of natural fiber humidity on the manufacturing. Table 2 summarizes the parameters set for the experiment and figure 4 shows the calculated Ca after based on the front velocity measurements for each plate.

Target Ca	Velocity v (m/s)	Flow rate Q (mL/min)
$1,0 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1,37 \cdot 10^{-4}$	2,93
$7,68 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1,05 \cdot 10^{-3}$	22,5
$2,0 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2,39 \cdot 10^{-3}$	51
$2,75 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3,76 \cdot 10^{-3}$	80

Table 2: Parameters for target Ca determination

The range of Capillary numbers studied allowed evaluation of the influence of flax fiber water content from low flow rate ($Q = 3 \text{ mL/min}$, $Ca = 1 \cdot 10^{-3}$) to high flow rate ($Q = 86 \text{ mL/min}$, $Ca = 2,75 \cdot 10^{-2}$). At low flow rate of resin (close to Ca_{opt}) fiber water content had a little effect on the flow front velocity since the target Ca was reached for all humidity levels. However, at higher flow rates, significant variations in the calculated Capillary number were observed, reflecting changes in flow front velocity. Although, preforms containing 7 - 10 wt% water content show the closest values to target capillary number. This result strengthens the idea of a strict control of the fiber water content during manufacturing.

3.3 A deformed preform after manufacturing

During several manufacturing trials, deformation of the preform was observed after resin impregnation. For example, the figure 5 shows the deformation of a 16.2wt% water content preform manufactured at the same flow rate of resin used during the validation of the method. The deformation of the preform can be a consequence of a high fiber water content and a high flow rate of resin. In order to show this phenomenon we built a phase diagram with the flow rate of resin and the fiber water content. The diagram is shown figure 6 and evidences the effect of a high capillary number and fiber water content on the preform during manufacturing.

Figure 5: Resin flow front progression through a preform with 16,2wt% water content

Cd_{target} (debit)	$1,00 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (3 mL/min)	$7,68 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (22,5 mL/min)	$2,00 \cdot 10^{-2}$ (54 mL/min)	$2,75 \cdot 10^{-2}$ (81 mL/min)
0 %wt (drying 103°C → 24h)				
7%wt (HR50%)				
10 %wt (HR70%)				
16 %wt (HR90%)				

Figure 6: Processability window

During impregnation, the resin applies a pressure on the fibrous preform in the thickness direction. As the resin progresses through the preform, the applied pressure increase. If this pressure exceeds the compaction (holding) pressure applied to the preform stack, the preform may slip, leading to deformation of the final part (figure 7).

Figure 7: Illustration of the threshold pressure phenomenon observed during the controlled infusion process

The threshold pressure can be calculated by using Terzaghi's law [12]. The threshold pressure is then assimilated to the effective stress in this case σ_{eff} .

$$\sigma_{eff} = \sigma_{tot} - P_0 \quad (1)$$

with σ_{eff} the effective stress in MPa, σ_{tot} the total stress applied on the preform in MPa and P_0 the pressure applied by the resin in MPa. P_0 is calculated using the following equation based on Darcy's law:

$$P_0 = (Q/A)^2 (\mu/K)t \quad (2)$$

with Q the flow rate of resin in m^3/s , A the section of the preform corrected by the volumetric fiber fraction in m^2 , μ the dynamic viscosity of the resin in Pa.s, K the permeability of the preform in m^2 and t is time in s.

In this study, permeability was taken as $K = 5.10^{-10} m^2$ based on previous work [13], [14]. For the total stress, a constant initial force of $\sigma_{tot} = 0.1$ MPa is applied. The preform relaxes during compaction, therefore, the total stress needed to reach target thickness decreases due to this relaxation and tends to an asymptotic value. A recent work of our team on NCF flax preform showed that the relaxation phenomenon increases with the fiber water content. Since this study is on 2 x 2 flax twill preform we approximate the total stress value in function of the preform water content following the table below.

Average water content wt%	Relaxed σ_{tot} (MPa)
0	0,08
7,6	0,07
9,9	0,06
16,7	0,05

Table 3: Values of the total stress σ_{tot} applied on the preform after relaxation for different preform water content

Effective stress has been calculated for various combination of flow rate and fiber water content and results are plotted in figure 8. It gives rise to a surface plot representing the threshold pressure, described as effective stress. When the pressure applied by the resin on the preform exceeds the value of effective stress, slippage occurs. This chart allows the manufacturer to know which thermo-hygrometric conditioning should be applied to the preform to allow manufacturing at target flow rate (Ca) without causing slippage of the preform.

Figure 8: 3D representation of effective stress calculation with flow rate and water content variations

3.3 Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of composites made with the *THMClight* at various water contents were assessed using flexural trial test. The stress at break and the flexural modulus have been plotted in an Ashby diagram (figure 8).

Figure 9: Effect of preform water content on mechanical properties of flax / epoxy composites

A clear degradation in both flexural modulus and flexural stress is observed as the moisture content increases from 0% to 16wt%. Composites produced from dry preforms (0wt%) exhibit the highest

mechanical performance, with an average flexural modulus of approximately 9 GPa and a flexural stress near 180 MPa. In contrast, composites manufactured with highly humid preforms (16wt%) show significantly reduced properties, with a modulus of ~6 GPa and strength below 130 MPa. However, we would like to point out the fact that the gap in mechanical performances between dry preform composites and 7wt% water content composites are not so different and can. Considering this, a composites reinforced by a preform that contains 7wt% can be suitable for a particular application. This brings the idea of a more reasonable conception of composite parts. If the drying phase is not mandatory to satisfy mechanical requirements then it should be avoid for cost and energy savings.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work we successfully developed a new research tool and a potential industrial method for composite part production. The *THMClight* system enables the manufacturing of composite plate at controlled flow rate of resin with a low-tech experimental setup. By controlling the flow rate, it becomes possible to maintain a constant resin flow front, allowing manufacturing at a target Capillary number and thus minimizing void content. Using this LCM method, the influence of natural fiber water content on manufacturing has been studied. Results showed that at optimal Ca , humidity has a limited effect on capillary number but at higher Ca significant variations can be observed. Due to hydrophilic nature of flax fiber, preform with high water content slipped during manufacturing at several flow rates. This was attributed to a decrease in permeability with increasing moisture content, leading to a higher fiber volume fraction. Consequently, the pressure exerted by the resin exceeded the compaction pressure from the mold, resulting in fiber movement. Mechanical testing revealed that composites made from dry preforms did not exhibit significantly superior properties compared to those made from preforms containing 5–7 wt% water. This opens the door to reconsidering the necessity of drying preforms prior to manufacturing. If mechanical requirements can be met without a drying phase, the process can be made more energy- and cost-efficient. By mastering the effect of water content during process it is then possible to avoid drying phase of preform that is energy consuming and cost effective for industrials. This will also reduce carbon footprint of natural fiber reinforce composite manufacturing.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank DEPESTELE/Teillage Vandecandelaère for their support and contribution to this work.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. A. Bachchan, P. P. Das, and V. Chaudhary, “Effect of moisture absorption on the properties of natural fiber reinforced polymer composites: A review,” *Mater. Today Proc.*, vol. 49, pp. 3403–3408, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2021.02.812.
- [2] S. Bickerton, Q. Govignon, and P. Kelly, “7 - Resin infusion/liquid composite moulding (LCM) of advanced fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP),” in *Advanced Fibre-Reinforced Polymer (FRP) Composites for Structural Applications*, J. Bai, Ed., in Woodhead Publishing Series in Civil and Structural Engineering. , Woodhead Publishing, 2013, pp. 155–186. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1533/9780857098641.2.155>.
- [3] A. Hindersmann, “Confusion about infusion: An overview of infusion processes,” *Compos. Part Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 126, p. 105583, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2019.105583.
- [4] C. H. Park, A. Lebel, A. Saouab, J. Bréard, and W. I. Lee, “Modeling and simulation of voids and saturation in liquid composite molding processes,” *Compos. Part Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 42, no. 6, pp. 658–668, Jun. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2011.02.005.
- [5] A. Céline, S. Fréour, F. Jacquemin, and P. Casari, “The hygroscopic behavior of plant fibers: a review,” *Front. Chem.*, vol. 1, 2014, doi: 10.3389/fchem.2013.00043.

- [6] M. Boutin, A. Rogeon, M. Aufray, R. Piquet, and A. Rouilly, "Influence of flax fibers on network formation of DGEBA/DETA matrix," *Compos. Interfaces*, vol. 28, no. 1, Art. no. 1, 2021, doi: 10.1080/09276440.2020.1736454.
- [7] J.-B. Jouenne, D. Barbier, V. Hounkpati, L. Cauret, and A. Vivet, "Influence of flax fibers on the curing kinetics of bio-based epoxy resin," *J. Mater. Sci.*, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s10853-024-09891-z.
- [8] S. Arnaud, "Contribution à la compréhension de la formation de défauts d'élaboration par RTM d'un composite stratifié Carbone/Epoxy – Influences sur le comportement hygrothermique et abattement des propriétés thermomécaniques," Université de Caen, 2013.
- [9] N. Patel, V. Rohatgi, and L. J. Lee, "Micro scale flow behavior and void formation mechanism during impregnation through a unidirectional stitched fiberglass mat," *Polym. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 35, no. 10, pp. 837–851, May 1995, doi: 10.1002/pen.760351006.
- [10] J. S. Leclerc and E. Ruiz, "Porosity reduction using optimized flow velocity in Resin Transfer Molding," *Compos. Part Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 39, no. 12, pp. 1859–1868, Dec. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2008.09.008.
- [11] G. Cazaux, "Faisabilité des procédés LCM pour l'élaboration de composites renfort continu à matrice thermoplastique polyamide," Université du Havre, 2016.
- [12] K. Terzaghi, *Theoretical Soil Mechanics*, John Wiley&Sons, Inc. 1943.
- [13] S. Comas-Cardona, P. Le Grogneq, C. Binetruy, and P. Krawczak, "Unidirectional compression of fibre reinforcements. Part 1: A non-linear elastic-plastic behaviour," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 67, no. 3–4, pp. 507–514, Mar. 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2006.08.017.
- [14] S. Comas-Cardona, C. Binetruy, and P. Krawczak, "Unidirectional compression of fibre reinforcements. Part 2: A continuous permeability tensor measurement," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 67, no. 3–4, pp. 638–645, Mar. 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2006.07.020.